

1 **06.06.2025, Sorbonne**

2 **Interviewee: Eugénia da Conceição**

3 **Interviewer: Filippo Martini**

4 S01: Okay, I'm going to start it here. So, I'm asking you to present
5 yourself and if you agree on the recording of the conversation. So, if
6 you'd like to state your name and to say...

7 S00: Okay, shall I simply state that I agree that you are recording the
8 interview. Yes, my name is Eugenia de Conceicao Heldt. I am professor in
9 European and Global Governance at the Technical University of Munich,
10 Department of Governance, and I've been working on negotiation analysis
11 over the past 20 years. I started my PhD on EU's negotiations by looking at
12 integrative and distributive bargaining situations in the EU by examining
13 how and why the common fisheries policy came into place. And that was
2003.

14 After that, I moved to negotiations at the WTO by looking at the impact of
15 domestic politics and bargaining dynamics in the bargaining outcomes.
16 Over
17 the past decade, I've been working more generally on international
18 organizations and European governance more broadly, but also on issues
19 such
20 as accountability and transparency in international negotiations.

19 S01: Okay, so, you're an academic, so you're a professor, so you're
20 teaching and researching these issues regarding negotiations, international
21 negotiation, and European negotiation, right?

22 S00: Yes, that's correct. Beyond that I am also interested in changes in
23 global economic governance. I have just edited a special issue in the
24 Review of International Political Economy on China's rise and the
25 reconfiguration of global economic governance. And I'm teaching that as
26 well, China's role in global economic governance, and I also have another
27 seminar looking at the political economy of the EU, where negotiation
28 analysis is one aspect, but it's broader than that. With my students we
29 look at the geopoliticization of EU governance across issue areas. As I
30 mentioned during the panel, the EU's Global Gateway, is one of the most
31 prominent geopolitical initiatives to counter the Chinese influence in the
32 Global Study as a global development financier. Another interesting area is
33 the transformation of the EU industrial policy from a market-based to a
34 securitization in the geoeconomic era. This is a way of explaining to
35 students what is going on right now in terms of great power competition
36 and
37 shifts in global economic governance.

37 S01: Maybe they will be able to be more vertical after they finish to study,
38 so maybe if they have a broader view.

39 S00: Exactly, yes, because, I mean, especially if you are a master's
40 student, you don't know yet what you want to do afterwards. Some of them
41 want to go to the diplomatic service, others want to work in the ministries
42 or European, at the European level, at the European Parliament, European
43 Commission, and so on. At this stage, it is important that you give them
44 broader tools or instruments that enable them to grasp what's going on or
45 in the world.

46 S01: Starting from that, I would like to shift a little bit more to Europe,
47 to focus on that. And about the systematic shifts we are having in Europe,
48 we are facing profound change, political, economic, social transformation
49 regarding climate changes and this kind of issue. And I would like to ask
50 you, which kind of this shift, in your opinion, has the greatest impact on
51 negotiation today?

52 S00: At the EU level, you mean? I think, basically, that the
53 geopoliticization of world politics and also the external shocks that we
54 are witnessing, such as the war in the Ukraine, but also the Israel-Gaza or
55 Israel-Palestina conflict. I can very briefly say a few words on the EU's
56 role as a global actor. First, why is the geopoliticization of world
57 politics important for the EU? In the current discussion, the rivalry
58 between the US and China is crucial. The EU, in turn, plays a secondary
59 role. The EU is trying to place itself in this new geopolitical landscape
60 by creating new geopolitical initiatives, such as the Global Gateway
61 Initiative, in which the EU uses its foreign economic policy as an
62 instrument by signing strategic trade and investment agreements. But also,
63 if you think about the enactment of the critical raw materials act, which
64 is basically having access to raw materials in the global south, in Africa,
65 in Latin America, in order to decrease its economic vulnerability vis-à-vis
66 China. The EU tries to place itself in this new geopolitical world and also
67 uses a more transactional approach in its foreign policy. A second crucial
68 issue is the EU's need to defend itself, because also transatlantic
69 relations were disrupted by the new Trump administration's stance on
70 NATO.

..1.1. Geopolitical

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..2.1. European

70 This was something unexpected for the EU. The EU member states were
71 very
72 surprised that the old friend suddenly was not willing or was threatening
73 to not defend Europe anymore. This can be an opportunity for Europe to
unite and work closely together on security and defense policy.

74 S01: Yeah, it's a matter of speech to grow up a little bit.

75 S00: Exactly.

76 S01: To finish, to be an adolescence and try to be an adult.

77 S00: Yes, exactly.

78 S00: Moving to the Israel-Palestina conflict, EU member states have
79 different positions on this issue hindering a common position at the
80 European level. You have countries closely aligned with Israel, such as
81 Germany, and others more critical, including Spain. But what is happening
82 right now in Gaza is a humanitarian catastrophe, and I think this is
83 challenging for the EU at different levels.

..2.1. European

..1.1. Geopolitical

84 S01: Thank you very much. I find it really interesting, from my point of
85 view, the fact that Europe didn't realize that maybe the USA would have not
86 been there for them, for us, because we have already been through the
87 Donald Trump first term, So maybe, I don't know why we have been caught
88 on
guard a little bit, maybe a bit naive if we put it in perspective.

..1.1. Geopolitical

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89 S00: It was naive, but at the same time we need to wait and see whether
90 Trump is going to change its behavior after the first year. It is still too
91 early to make definitive statements. Nevertheless, the EU needs to

..1.1. Geopolitical	92	emancipate itself by becoming responsible for its own security. Member
	93	states have been discussing this over the past 10 years. This is not
	94	something new or coming from Trump. Already under the Obama
	95	administration,
..1.1. Geopolitical	96	the US had put some pressure on EU member states urging them to spend
	97	more
	98	on defense. But of course, it was a different time and a different context,
	99	and nobody thought that Russia would be such an aggressive actor,
		challenging frontiers and reverting the world and the frontiers after the
		end of the Soviet Union.
	100	S01: I also remember Angela Merkel and the Belarusian statement about,
	101	after Trump, the first time of Trump, statement about regarding EU's
	102	necessity to think about defending, be able to defend itself. So that's why
	103	I think maybe not something that could not be forecasted, but as you were
	104	saying,
	105	S00: This is a big shift that requires adaptation from EU member states.
..1.1. Geopolitical	106	Europe was in a very comfortable situation, in the sense that the US was
	107	paying for its security, for European security. And European, or Western
	108	European countries were able to develop a stronger welfare state, and now
	109	we have the situation that the member states need to find a balance
	110	between
		still keeping the welfare state but shifting resources to defense.
	111	S01: This is very interesting. Going to the next question, it looks like
	112	this is a very tough negotiation between state members. Yes. I would like
	113	to ask you, for your point of view, what is the most demanding negotiation
	114	in which you have the task to participate, or in which you have been an
	115	observer?
	116	S00: If we look at the current world situation, I think it's not really a
..3.1.1. Challenges	117	formal negotiation, but it's how to react or how to negotiate with an
	118	erratic and unpredictable actors in the world stage. Just think about how
	119	difficult it is for the European Commission to negotiate trade tariffs with
	120	the US.
	121	S01: So not just a single negotiation, but a framework in which the other
	122	part is a difficult person.
	123	S00: Well, yes, exactly. The main challenge is that the negotiating
	124	positions change very quickly.
	125	S01: Going back, instead of talking about the conference, the conference is
	126	trying to create bridges also between the worlds: the academic world and
	127	the practitioner world. What do you think about, what's your point of view
	128	about the biggest gap between the two worlds, the academic world and the
	129	practitioner world?
..4.1. Research / Practi	130	S00: The academic and the practitioner worlds are quite different. While
	131	practitioners need to provide very quickly responses to politicians,
..4.1. Research / Pra	132	academics provide a long-term analytical perspective by contextualizing
	133	facts in more-depth. Sometimes it is difficult to find a common language
	134	and to engage in a dialogue because we speak to different audiences.
..4.1. Research / Practi	135	Academics are more concerned about explaining a certain behavior or
	136	outcome (negotiation outcome). By contrast, practitioners need to find very
	137	quickly a solution for the politicians because the media, the public

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..4.1. Research / Practi	162
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..2.1. European	174
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opinion, or the voters are waiting. Sometimes, it is difficult for academics to realize under which pressure practitioners are working.

S01: Interesting also the fact that we are, lots of time talking about the public, that we are subject to more pressure because the social media is going to be very, very quick. Yeah. And, well, from my point of view in Italy, really can clearly see that because we are always in a shift of power, very quickly. Yeah. So, it's interesting to, to have a different point of view from, from your point of view.

S01: And, what do you think about the possibility to trying to, decrease the gap? How we could do that?

S00: I think that this initiative, uh, by Francesco Marchi in bringing together practitioners and academics is a good step forward or it's a, a, a very good beginning. And I think that our panel was really very productive and constructive in the sense that we had someone from the Commission, who

basically confirmed our findings. But at the end of the day, it's a trade-off because sometimes academics, they just stay in their bubble. Engaging with practitioners is not a priority for many academics. We have to prepare the next paper to be presented in academic preferences, engage with our peers, etc. It is a trade-off, you have to select who is your audience and it is practically impossible to attend academic conferences and at the same time engage with the the practitioners' world. It also really depends also on where you are in your career, whether you have time to attend this kind of conferences, and whether you consider them a priority. What are the costs and benefits of engaging with different communities and do you have the time to do it. It can be interesting to engage with practitioners, but it is also difficult to find a common language and to stay in touch afterwards.

S01: A common language is a sentence I like it, because, it came up a few times more time, because, we need to find a common language, we need to build it's interesting to think about the communication between academic world, and the practitioner's one, as an negotiation itself, in which we need to try to understand which are the interests, and how create common value. So, yes. Common language is really important also for this kind of situation, for, as far as I can tell. Coming back to the Europe do you think that it could be perceived different, in negotiation, from the rest of the world?

S00: It's a very general question. I think, the Europe or the European Union is a step forward compared to other parts, of the world. If you, if you think about the European Union, with member states giving up competences to the supranational, to the European level, this is quite unique. In other parts of the world and at the international level you have intergovernmental coordination and cooperation, but you don't have the abdication of sovereignty, and this is basically what we have in the EU in some policy areas. The EU is also a role model for other regional organizations, including Mercosur or ASEAN. I would say this is what is unique in Europe, we had two world wars and at that time, politicians, realized the only way forward was to be together, to act jointly. There have been many setbacks, because the preferences are diverge. However, Europe is a united continent with a single market, a joint currency, the Euro, and supranational institutions acting on behalf of EU Member States,

	188	such as the European Commission. However, we also have the legacy of
	189	colonialism, making it sometimes very difficult to find a common ground
	190	with countries in Latin America, in Africa, but also in Asia. Several
..3.1.1. Challenges	191	European countries are still seen as former colonialists. Sometimes it is
	192	better to have the European Commission as a neutral entity acting and
	193	negotiating on behalf of EU member states with many of these countries.
	194	This is another complex dimension of European power.
	195	S01: It needs to be addressed, to be aware of why, and for the preparation
	196	part. And about, what do you think about a skill that a negotiator for
	197	tomorrow should have, or should they build?
	198	S00: I think it's very important to show respect, or to treat the other
..5.1. Essential Skills a	199	parties in a respectful way, and also to put himself or herself in the
	200	shoes of the other. Basically, a negotiator needs to show empathy. I think
	201	that respect (or the respectful treatment of the other) and empathy are two
	202	crucial skills for the future and for the present.
	203	S01: Yeah, I like this, I really like to put respect at the center. It
	204	could seem to be a bit simple, but it's not at all, because we tend to
	205	forget, we tend to try to learn tools, to learn frameworks, and then we
	206	forget that we need to engage, we are human, so we need to establish a
	207	relationship, and to be able to do that, we need to, not just to be
	208	empathetic, but also to be respectful. So, I really like that your answer.
..5.1. Essential Skills a	209	S00: Yes, it sounds easy to be respectful and emphatic, but it's very
	210	difficult to implement them in a specific negotiating setting.
	211	S01: It was, I got a similar reply by Jack Cambria. I was asking what he
	212	thought about, the most important thing from his point of view, his long
	213	experience, about negotiation, and he replied, yes, it's pretty simple, you
	214	need to be respectful.
	215	S00: Happy to hear that there is some confluence in the responses that you
	216	are getting. Respect is a very important aspect of then being able to have
	217	a successful outcome.
	218	S01: And we are almost finished and thank you again your time. I would
	219	stick a little bit to the concept of respect. How would you think that
	220	would be, we can learn to do that?
..5.3. Teaching Method	221	S00: I mean, simply listening also to the other part, negotiating partner,
	222	or party, and simply trying to understand what they, their concerns are.
	223	And sometimes, just by listening you can realize, what are the issues, when
	224	the other parties have the impression that they are not been taken into
	225	consideration.
	226	S01: And what negotiation question, you'd wish for scholar or practitioners
	227	would tackle next? Basically, which research questions are still to be
	228	answered.
..6.1. Research Question	229	S00: Well, one, one question, uh, is basically how the coalitions, formal
	230	and informal coalitions build in negotiating processes? And why do they
	231	end?
	232	S01: Maybe it could be something that you could address in the future.

233 S00: Yes, yes, you just need time.

234 S01: And the last question is lighter, but I think it could be interesting.
235 If you could recommend a book and a movie regarding negotiation?

236 S00: Okay, yes. Well, I don't have a movie on negotiations, but I think if
237 you want to understand how politics work, you can start with the Netflix
238 series, House of Cards, is really an eye-opener in the sense that it shows
239 how complex politics can be. But I don't have a suggestion for a film or a
240 movie on negotiations. I think this could work. Yes, it's not basically
241 about the international level, it's more about domestic politics. In terms
242 of a seminal study or an introduction to negotiation analysis, I would
243 suggest to start with Raiffa's classic book "Negotiation Analysis: The
244 Science and Art of Collaborative Decision Making." It's really one of the
245 best introductory books in the field. It gives you a general overview of
246 all the important issues in a negotiation, namely who are the actors, what
247 are the issues at stake, what are their preferences, what kind of demands
248 do they have, what negotiating strategies and tactics do they use, and so
249 on.

250 S01: So, thank you very much again for your time.

251 S00: My pleasure.

252 S01: We are just finished, so I'm going to stop recording.